

Psychoactive products market observation

Annual review

E-publication containing information on new substances on the market, methods of synthesis, consumer forms and transport forms recorded during AIP SIN monitoring.

Established with the participation of leading experts in the field of combating illicit drug trafficking in the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation

Issue 71

November 2025

Authors:

Ruslan Yurchenko
Lubov Yurchenko
Inna Haletskaya
Matsvei Navitski
Yury Pavlovets
Anastasiya Piatsetskaya

Contents

Materials prepared by AIPSIN team on the basis of open sources and their own researches.

- I. New substances on the market;
- II. Psychoactive plants, mushrooms and their products which identified on the market;
- III. Recognition of substances as new psychoactive substances by competent authorities;
- IV. Substances used in the synthesis of psychoactive products;
- V. Complex composition objects which detected on the market;
- VI. "Grey" market substances and objects on the market;
- VII. Change in the control status of substances and objects;
- VIII. Doping substances;
- IX. Renewed consumer interest in neglected psychoactive substances/objects;
- X. Adulterants;
- XI. Substances and objects whose properties and control may be in doubt;
- XII. Seizures and/or consumption facts of precursors, psychoactive substances and objects on the territory of CIS countries;
- XIII. New consumer and transport forms of psychoactive substances and precursors.

Information provided in AIPСIN alerts:

1. Formed based on the results of:

- monitoring of available open sources, including: the range of psychoactive products trading sites; research reports on real objects; specialised scientific journals, patents both for compounds themselves and for certain classes of chemical compounds having a structure similar to that of already controlled narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors, as well as non-controlled compounds already widely used for recreational purposes; reports of drug users on specialised forums on the manufacture of psychoactive products; information provided by users of the system in various government agencies in a number of countries, both in the form of one-off requests, reports, applications, and also in the form of information provided by users of the system.
- studying information provided by users of the system from various government agencies in a number of countries, both in the form of one-off requests, reports, applications and on a contractual basis;
- analysing the results of automatic identification and queries within the framework of work with the Web-version of the system.

2. **It is informational in nature** and does not claim to be comprehensive enough to make a decision on the need to establish state control over the turnover of relevant chemicals, plant objects and mushrooms;

3. **It is intended for competent specialists** who have reliable information on the structure, conditions and trends of the psychoactive products market of the respective state to assess the probability of distribution of substances and objects identified in the course of AIPСIN monitoring on its territory;

4. In order to make a decision on the necessity to establish state control over the circulation of relevant chemical substances, plant objects and mushrooms **requires additional analysis by specialists** with access to relevant specialised information on the presence or absence of confirmed facts of their circulation and (or) abuse with the purpose of obtaining a psychoactive effect in a particular territory.

Attention:

Issuers of alerts reserve the right to specify those sources and to the extent that, from their point of view, are sufficient for a preliminary assessment of the social danger of the substances and objects described.

In order to prevent the loss of information that initialises the appearance of the alert (pages of online shops, chat rooms, forums), some sources are archived and stored together with the alert in the Web-version of the IPS "AIPСIN Anti-Drugs".

The control status of the substance or object specified in the alert corresponds to the date of its issuance.

Publishers consider the fulfilment of one or more conditions as sufficient grounds for the issuance of an alert:

- Identification of information on the seizure of a substance or notification object from circulation by law enforcement agencies, regardless of the control status of a particular territory;
- identification of information on the identification by expert units of law enforcement agencies of the substance or notification object submitted for examination;
- Identification of information on the identification by experts/specialists of the Ministry of Health or the Ministry of Justice of the fact of consumption of the substance or notification object;
- identification of information on the identification of the substance or notification object in samples submitted by consumers;
- identification of information from authorised monitoring services of different States on seizures/seizures in circulation/consumption/facts of consumption/availability of the substance or alert object on the market;
- change in the control status of the substance or alert object in any of the countries being monitored;
- a description of the fact of consumption of the substance or notification object, publicised by the consumer in one form or another;
- information on the appearance of offers to sell the substance or alert object on psychoactive product marketplaces;
- Identification of literature or patent information on the activity of the alert substance and its similarity to the activity of controlled substances.

The publishers reserve the right, based on their own experience and consultations with external specialists and representatives of competent authorities, to assess the social danger and describe the facts in a probabilistic manner. The purpose of the alerts in this case is to draw the attention of competent personnel to the POSSIBILITY of psychoactive substances appearing in circulation in order for them to independently assess the social danger potential of the alert objects in question.

Content

I. New substances on the market.....	2
603. 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate (2,6-dichloro-3-fluoro Etomidate).....	3
605. ABP-700 (Cyclopropyl-methoxycarbonyl Metomidate)	5
612. α -BPVP (4-phenyl- α -Pyrrolidinopentiophenone).....	7
613. 1Fe-LSD.....	9
604. Ethylflualprazolam.....	11
606. N-Desethyl-5-cyanoprotodesnitazene (N-desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene)	13
607. 2-Fluonitazene (2'-fluoro Nitazene)	15
608. Zolpidic N,N-diethylamide (Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide).....	17
609. 3-Fluonitazene (3'-fluoro Nitazene)	19
610. N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene	21
611. 4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene (5-cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene)	23
IV. Substances used in the synthesis of psychoactive products.....	25
80. 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene and 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene	26
VII. Change in the control status of substances and objects.....	28
331. The list of potent substances in the Russian Federation has been updated.	29
332. Changes have been made to the lists of narcotic and psychotropic substances in the Republic of Lithuania.	38
X. Adulterants.....	45
268. Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC)	46
269. 4-HO-MET (Methocin)	48
270. Pregabalin.....	50
XII. Seizures and/or consumption facts of precursors, psychoactive substances and objects on the territory of CIS countries;.....	52
133. Synthetic hashish.....	53

I. New substances on the market

603. 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate (2,6-dichloro-3-fluoro Etomidate)

I.A. Substances whose structure has been confirmed

Active ingredient: 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate (2,6-dichloro-3-fluoro Etomidate)

Nomenclature name: Ethyl 1-[1-(2,6-dichloro-3-fluorophenyl)ethyl]-1H-imidazole-5-carboxylate

Molecular Formula: C₁₄H₁₃Cl₂FN₂O₂

Molecular weight: 331.17

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In May 2025, a single offer for the sale of the substance 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate (2,6-dichloro-3-fluoro Etomidate) as an analytical standard was identified on the trading platform Cayman Chemical.

The compound 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate, based on its chemical structure, belongs to a new and poorly studied group of substances on the recreational market, provisionally named "Etomidates." The group is named after the most well-known of the phenylethylimidazoles — Etomidate, which was originally a pharmaceutical substance, a short-acting intravenous general anesthetic. 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate is a structural analog of Etomidate, Metomidate, as well as Propoxate, Isopropoxate, Butomidate, the appearance of which on the market [we have reported](#).

Slightly earlier, we also reported the appearance of the substance [iso-Butomidate](#) on the Cayman Chemical trading platform.

These substances began appearing on markets primarily in countries that started tightening control over the non-medical use of Etomidate. Recently, Etomidate and its analogs have frequently been found on illegal drug markets in East and Southeast Asian countries. As a rule, the substances are detected in e-liquid compositions.

In China, Etomidate began to be detected in e-liquids after synthetic cannabinoids were placed under control in 2021. Quite logically, after establishing control over Etomidate in October 2023, its analogs such as Metomidate, Isopropoxate, and Propoxate began to be identified in China. Since January 2024, the country has seen an increase in cases of detecting its analogs, especially Propoxate and Isopropoxate. Quite naturally, in July 2024, they were also placed under control in China, and in July 2025, [2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate](#) was placed under control as well. In March 2025, UNODC published a report "The increase in detections of etomidate and its analogues on illicit drug markets is becoming a global problem," which indicated a rise in the number of cases of detecting Etomidate and its analogs on illegal drug markets.

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate is absent. Based on structural similarity with other phenylethylimidazoles, it can be assumed that 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate will also act as a short-acting anesthetic. A paper was recently published reporting the first identification of the substance in question in seized e-liquids. The paper characterized the compound's structure using GC-MS, HPLC-MS/MS with QTRAP, NMR, and IR-Fourier spectroscopy methods. Given that this substance is an analog of Etomidate, this study used SwissADME and ProTox-3.0 software to predict its pharmacokinetic data in comparison with Etomidate, allowing a preliminary assessment of its potential toxicity. Predictions show that, similar to Etomidate, this substance may pose risks associated with neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, and respiratory toxicity in cases of abuse.

Against the backdrop of continued heightened interest in new designer drugs, the compound 2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate has high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44147/plus-minus-2-6-dichloro-3-fluoro-etomidate>
2. <https://aip sin.com/newsubstance/1771/>
3. Hong Song, Li Wu, Boyang Xu, Hongjian Zhang, Jianhong Gao, Identification and structural elucidation of 2,6-dichloro-3-fluoroetomidate: A new psychoactive substance in e-liquids, Forensic Science International Volume 378, February 2026, 112684, doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2025.112684

Alert publication date: 03.11.2025

605. ABP-700 (Cyclopropyl-methoxycarbonyl Metomidate)

I.A. Substances whose structure has been confirmed

Active ingredient: ABP-700 (Cyclopropyl-methoxycarbonyl Metomidate)

Nomenclature name: 1-(Methoxycarbonyl)cyclopropyl 1-(1-phenylethyl)-1H-imidazole-5-carboxylate

Molecular Formula: C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₄

Molecular weight: 314.34

Russian Federation: ABP-700 turnover control is not installed.

Republic of Belarus: ABP-700 turnover control is not installed.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [ABP-700](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In November 2025, an offer for the sale of the substance ABP-700 (Cyclopropyl-methoxycarbonyl Metomidate) as an analytical standard was identified on the trading platform Cayman Chemical.

The compound ABP-700, based on its chemical structure, belongs to a new and poorly studied group of substances on the recreational market, provisionally named "Etomidates." The group is named after the most well-known of the phenylethylimidazoles — Etomidate, which was originally a pharmaceutical substance, a short-acting intravenous general anesthetic. ABP-700 is a structural analog of Etomidate, Metomidate, as well as Propoxate, Isopropoxate, Butomidate, the appearance of which on the market [we have reported](#). Earlier we also reported the appearance of substances [iso-Butomidate \(iso-Butomidate\)](#) and [2,6-diCl-3F-Etomidate](#) on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. These substances began appearing on markets primarily in countries that started tightening control over the non-medical use of Etomidate. Recently, Etomidate and its analogs have

frequently been found on illegal drug markets in East and Southeast Asian countries. As a rule, the substances are detected in e-liquid compositions.

In China, Etomidate began to be detected in e-liquids after synthetic cannabinoids were placed under control in 2021. Quite logically, after establishing control over Etomidate in October 2023, its analogs such as Metomidate, Isopropoxate, and Propoxate began to be identified in China. Since January 2024, the country has seen an increase in cases of detecting its analogs, especially Propoxate and Isopropoxate. Quite naturally, in July 2024, they were also placed under control in China.

In March 2025, UNODC published a report "The increase in detections of etomidate and its analogues on illicit drug markets is becoming a global problem," which indicated a rise in the number of cases of detecting Etomidate and its analogs on illegal drug markets. Research has shown that ABP-700 acts on the GABAA receptor and has a high hypnotic effect, exhibiting hemodynamic stability, rapid metabolism, and ultra-short duration of action.

Against the backdrop of continued heightened interest in new designer drugs, the compound ABP-700 has high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44146/cyclopropyl-methoxycarbonyl-metomidate>
2. Raymond J Malapero, Michael P Zaccagnino, Ethan Y Brovman, Alan David Kaye, Richard D Urman, Etomidate derivatives: Novel pharmaceutical agents in anesthesia, J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol. 2017 Oct-Dec;33(4):429–431. [doi: 10.4103/0970-9185.222521](https://doi.org/10.4103/0970-9185.222521)

Alert publication date: 05.11.2025

612. α -BPVP (4-phenyl- α -Pyrrolidinopentiophenone)

I.A. Substances whose structure has been confirmed

Active ingredient: α -BPVP (4-phenyl- α -Pyrrolidinopentiophenone)

Nomenclature name: 1-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)-2-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)pentan-1-one

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₂₅NO

Molecular weight: 307.43

Russian Federation: α -BPVP – Schedule I Narcotic drugs, subject to control as a derivative of N-methylephedrone.

Republic of Belarus: control over the turnover of α -BPVP has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: α -BPVP.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound α -BPVP (4-phenyl- α -Pyrrolidinopentiophenone) is a synthetic phenylalkylamine of the cathinone subgroup, a structural analog of psychoactive substances α -PVP, α -PHP (α -Pyrrolidinohexanophenone), whose circulation is under International Control (Schedule II of the 1971 Convention on Psychotropic Substances).

In mid-2025, an article was published reporting the identification of a new psychoactive substance with a cathinone structure and a biphenyl substituent, detected in a powder seized on the black market. The packaging with the powder was labeled as "a-BVPV". Identification and characterization of the substance in the seized powder were conducted using various analytical methods, such as GC-MS with electron impact ionization, high-resolution mass spectrometry with an orbital trap (HRAM-Orbitrap-MS), and one-dimensional and two-dimensional NMR analysis. Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of α -BPVP is absent. Based on structural similarity with other psychoactive cathinones, it can be assumed that α -BPVP may also have a stimulating effect.

First discussions about the properties of the substance appeared on specialized forums about 10 months ago. According to user descriptions, the substance is not as potent as α -PVP, but effects are present, "a decent stimulant, approximately at the dosage level of NEP (N-Ethylnorpentedrone) or slightly more potent...". In autumn 2025, isolated offers of the substance were recorded on trading internet platforms for recreational products, including on the Cayman Chemical trading platform as an analytical standard in salt form (hydrochloride). Against the backdrop of continued heightened interest in new designer drugs, the compound α -BPVP has high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/43885/4-phenyl-alpha-pyrrolidinopentiophenone-hydrochloride>
2. Sara Casati, Roberta F. Bergamaschi, Riccardo Primavera, Alessandro Ravelli, Ivana Lavota, Alessio Battistini, Identification and Structural Elucidation of a Novel Pyrrolidinophenone-Based Designer Drug on the Illicit Market: α -BPVP, Chem. Res. Toxicol. 2025, 38, 808–811, doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.5c00068
3. <https://drsupply.nl/ru/>
4. https://www.reddit.com/r/researchchemicals/comments/1jleu5f/abpvp_first_time_i_love_being_the_only_guinea_pig/?tl=ru

Alert publication date: 18.11.2025

613. 1Fe-LSD

I.A. Substances whose structure has been confirmed

Active ingredient: 1Fe-LSD

Nomenclature name: (8 β)-1-ferrocenecarbonyl-N,N-diethyl-6-methyl-9,10-didehydroergoline-8-carboxamide hemi-L-tartrate

Molecular Formula: C₃₁H₃₄N₃O₂Fe

Molecular weight: 536.46

Russian Federation: 1Fe-LSD - List I Narcotic drugs, subject to control as a derivative of Lysergic acid.

Republic of Belarus: 1Fe-LSD circulation control is not installed.

Learn more in AIP SIN: 1Fe-LSD

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In November 2025, an offer for a new lysergamide, 1Fe-LSD, in the form of blotter papers (dose 200 μ g) and micro-pellets with a diameter of 3 mm (dose 300 μ g) of orange color was recorded on one of the German trading internet platforms for psychoactive products.

The compound 1Fe-LSD, based on its chemical structure, is a synthetic tryptamine of the lysergide subgroup, a structural analog of a whole range of new lysergamides that have been actively appearing on the market recently: [1BS-LSD](#), [1H-LSD](#), [1Bz-LSD](#). The composition of 1Fe-LSD includes ferrocene - an iron compound that gives it its name. Ferrocene is an organometallic compound of orange color, which explains the color of the blotter papers and pellets.

No available data on the pharmacological properties and toxicity of the compound were found. Based on structural similarity with other known lysergides, it can be assumed that 1Fe-LSD will exhibit affinity for serotonin receptors and will be characterized by hallucinogenic (psychedelic) properties. Also, based on information provided in scientific publications about similar analogs, 1Fe-LSD can be considered as a "prodrug" of LSD. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://lsd-legal.de/shop/200mcg-1fe-lsd-full-blotter/>
2. https://www.reddit.com/r/LSD/comments/1p789ns/1felsd_as_a_new_legal_derivative_in_germany_based/

Alert publication date: 27.11.2025

604. Ethylflualprazolam

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: Ethylflualprazolam

Nomenclature name: 8-Chloro-1-ethyl-6-(2-fluorophenyl)-4H-benzo[f][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a][1,4]diazepine

Molecular Formula: C₁₈H₁₄ClFN₄

Molecular weight: 340.79

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of ethylflualprazolam has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of ethylflualprazolam has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: Ethylflualprazolam.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound Ethylflualprazolam, based on its chemical structure, is a benzodiazepine, a derivative of Flualprazolam, whose circulation is controlled in most countries, including under International control (Schedule IV of the 1971 Convention on Psychotropic Substances), and which is actively used for recreational purposes. It is also an analog of a whole range of long-known benzodiazepines: Alprazolam, Estazolam, Flunitrazepam, and many others.

No available data on the pharmacological properties and toxicity of the compound have been found yet. Based on structural similarity with Flualprazolam and other benzodiazepines, it can be assumed that Ethylflualprazolam will also exhibit affinity for GABAA receptors and possess properties of an anxiolytic, sedative, and hypnotic agent. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the substance in question has so far yielded no results.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of the substance Ethylflualprazolam as an analytical standard was presented on the CaymanChemical trading platform.

Against the backdrop of continued heightened interest in new designer benzodiazepines, Ethylflualprazolam has high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44429/ethylflualprazolam>

Alert publication date: 04.11.2025

606. N-Desethyl-5-cyanoprotodesnitazene (N-desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene)

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: N-Desethyl-5-cyanoprotodesnitazene (N-desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene)

Nomenclature name: 1-(2-(Ethylamino)ethyl)-2-(4-propoxybenzyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-5-carbonitrile

Molecular Formula: C₂₂H₂₆N₄O

Molecular weight: 362.21

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of N-Desethyl-5-cyanoprotodesnitazene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of N-Desethyl-5-cyanoprotodesnitazene has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: N-desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene, based on its chemical structure, belongs to the opioids of the 2-benzylbenzimidazole family. It has structural similarity to Protonitazene, whose circulation is controlled in many countries, including under International control (Narcotic Drugs, included in Schedule I of the 1961 Convention). It is also an analog of a whole range of 5-cyano-nitazenes that have been appearing en masse in 2025, for example, [5-Cyanoisotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoprotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanometodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoetazene](#).

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene, as well as a whole range of its analogs, is absent. It is known that its analog 5-Cyanoetazene, which

was detected in recreational products in Germany in 2021, is described as having "reduced, but still significant" activity compared to Etonitazene. Taking this fact into account and based on the structural similarity of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene to other, more studied opioids, it can be assumed that it will also act as a μ -opioid receptor agonist. Also, based on the published metabolism of Isotonitazene, it can be assumed that N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene is a potential metabolite of [5-Cyanoprotodesnitazene](#), the appearance of which we reported earlier.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene in the form of hydrochloride salt as an analytical standard was identified on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the substance in question has so far yielded no results.

Against the backdrop of heightened interest in new designer opioids and the widespread banning of fentanyl, benzimidazoles in general, and N-Desethyl 5-cyano Protodesnitazene in particular, have high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44322/n-desethyl-5-cyano-protodesnitazene-hydrochloride>

Alert publication date: 10.11.2025

607. 2-Fluonitazene (2'-fluoro Nitazene)

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: 2-Fluonitazene (2'-fluoro Nitazene)

Nomenclature name: N,N-diethyl-2-(2-(2-fluorobenzyl)-5-nitro-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)ethan-1-amine

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₂₃FN₄O₂

Molecular weight: 370.18

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 2-Fluonitazene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 2-Fluonitazene has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: 2-Fluonitazene.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound 2'-Fluoro Nitazene, based on its chemical structure, belongs to the opioids of the 2-benzylbenzimidazole family. It is a positional isomer (by fluorine atom position) of [Flunitazene](#), for which an official notification was made in 2020, and a structural analog of Clonitazene, subject to International control (Narcotic Drugs, included in Schedule I of the 1961 Convention).

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of 2'-Fluoro Nitazene, as well as a whole range of its analogs, is absent. Based on its structural similarity to Flunitazene, which is known to be a μ -opioid receptor agonist with analgesic activity comparable to morphine, it can be assumed that 2'-Fluoro Nitazene will also be characterized by properties of a μ -opioid receptor agonist.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of 2'-Fluoro Nitazene in the form of hydrochloride salt as an analytical standard was identified on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the substance in question has so far yielded no results.

Against the backdrop of heightened interest in new designer opioids and the widespread banning of fentanyls, benzimidazoles in general, and 2'-Fluoro Nitazene in particular, have high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44673/2-prime-fluoro-nitazene-hydrochloride2>
2. <https://aipsin.com/newsubstance/588/>

Alert publication date: 11.11.2025

608. Zolpidic N,N-diethylamide (Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide)

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: Zolpidic N,N-diethylamide (Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide)

Nomenclature name: N,N-Diethyl-2-[6-methyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-yl]acetamide

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₂₅N₃O

Molecular weight: 335.44

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of Zolpidic N,N-diethylamide has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of Zolpidic N,N-diethylamide has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide, based on its chemical structure, is an imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine, having structural similarity to Zolpidem, which is under International control (Schedule IV of the 1971 Convention on Psychotropic Substances). Zolpidem is a non-benzodiazepine sedative-hypnotic agent (one of the so-called "Z-drugs"), sold under the trade name "Ambien," among others, and used for both short-term treatment of insomnia and for recreational purposes. Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide differs from Zolpidem by the replacement of the N,N-dimethyl radical with an N,N-diethyl radical. Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide is also a derivative of [N-Ethylzolpidem](#), for which an official notification was made in 2022. It has structural similarity to other "Z-drugs": Zopiclone, Zaleplon, and Pagoclone.

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide is absent. Based on its structural similarity to Zolpidem and other "Z-drugs," it can be assumed that Zolpidic N,N-Diethyl Amide exerts sedative and hypnotic effects.

The compound was first recorded in mid-2025 on one of the chemical product websites. In November, the first user description of substance use appeared on a specialized forum. According to descriptions, the effect of the substance at a dose of about 7 mg orally occurred instantly. The substance differs from traditional zolpidem in that the benzo-like effects are less pronounced, but it helps with falling asleep and sleeping longer than traditional zolpidem. There is also a hangover, but it is not severe at all and quite functional. It is recommended to dose the substance carefully when using, as a dose of 10 mg may cause slight amnesia. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://syntharise.com/products-page/n-ethyl-2-6-methyl-2-4-methylphenylimidazo12-apyridin-3-ylacetamide/n-n-diethyl-zolpidem/>
2. https://www.reddit.com/r/researchchemicals/comments/1ouhg06/experience_report_on_zolpidem_analog_zolpidic/
3. <https://aipsin.com/newsubstance/910/>

Alert publication date: 13.11.2025

609. 3-Fluonitazene (3'-fluoro Nitazene)

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: 3-Fluonitazene (3'-fluoro Nitazene)

Nomenclature name: N,N-Diethyl-2-(2-(3-fluorobenzyl)-5-nitro-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)ethan-1-amine

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₂₃FN₄O₂

Molecular weight: 370.18

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 3-Fluonitazene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 3-Fluonitazene has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: 3-Fluonitazene.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound 3'-Fluoro Nitazene, based on its chemical structure, belongs to the opioids of the 2-benzylbenzimidazole family. It is a positional isomer (by fluorine atom position) of [Flunitazene](#), for which an official notification was made in 2020, and a structural analog of Clonitazene, subject to International control (Narcotic Drugs, included in Schedule I of the 1961 Convention).

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of 3'-Fluoro Nitazene, as well as a whole range of its analogs, is absent. Based on its structural similarity to Flunitazene, which is known to be a μ -opioid receptor agonist with analgesic activity comparable to morphine, it can be assumed that 3'-Fluoro Nitazene will also be characterized by properties of a μ -opioid receptor agonist.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of 3'-Fluoro Nitazene in the form of hydrochloride salt as an analytical standard was identified on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the

substance in question has so far yielded no results. Slightly earlier, the compound [2'-Fluoro Nitazene](#) also appeared on the Cayman Chemical trading platform as an analytical standard, which we reported. Against the backdrop of heightened interest in new designer opioids and the widespread banning of fentanyl, benzimidazoles in general, and 3'-Fluoro Nitazene in particular, have high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44674/3-prime-fluoro-nitazene-hydrochloride>
2. <https://aipsin.com/newsubstance/1854/>

Alert publication date: 14.11.2025

610. N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene (N-desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene)

Nomenclature name: 1-(2-(Ethylamino)ethyl)-2-(4-isopropoxybenzyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-5-carbonitrile

Molecular Formula: C₂₂H₂₆N₄O

Molecular weight: 362.47

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [N-Desethyl-5-cyanoisotodesnitazene](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene, based on its chemical structure, belongs to the opioids of the 2-benzylbenzimidazole family. It has structural similarity to Isotonitazene, whose circulation is controlled in many countries, including under International control (Narcotic Drugs, included in Schedule I of the 1961 Convention). It is also an analog of a whole range of 5-cyano-nitazenes that have been appearing en masse in 2025, for example, [5-Cyanoisotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoprotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanometodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoetazene](#).

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene, as well as a whole range of its analogs, is absent. It is known that its analog 5-Cyanoetazene, which was detected in recreational products in Germany in 2021, is described as having "reduced, but still

significant" activity compared to Etonitazene. Taking this fact into account and based on the structural similarity of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene to other, more studied opioids, it can be assumed that it will also act as a μ -opioid receptor agonist. Also, based on the published metabolism of Isotonitazene, it can be assumed that N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene is a potential metabolite of [5-Cyanoisotodesnitazene](#), the appearance of which we reported earlier.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene in the form of hydrochloride salt as an analytical standard was identified on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the substance in question has so far yielded no results. Against the backdrop of heightened interest in new designer opioids and the widespread banning of fentanyls, benzimidazoles in general, and N-Desethyl 5-cyano Isotodesnitazene in particular, have high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/44321/n-desethyl-5-cyano-isotodesnitazene-hydrochloride>

Alert publication date: 17.11.2025

611. 4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene (5-cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene)

I.D. Substances with a confirmed structure that have been mentioned only once

Active ingredient: 4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene (5-cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene)

Nomenclature name: 1-(2-(Diethylamino)ethyl)-2-(4-hydroxybenzyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-5-carbonitrile

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₂₄N₄O

Molecular weight: 348.44

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [4-Hydroxy-5-cyanoethazene](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene, based on its chemical structure, belongs to the opioids of the 2-benzylbenzimidazole family. It has structural similarity to Metonitazene, whose circulation is controlled in many countries, including under International control (Narcotic Drugs, included in Schedule I of the 1961 Convention), and [Metodesnitazene](#) (official notification made in 2020). It is also an analog of a whole range of 5-cyano-nitazenes that have been appearing en masse in 2025, for example, [5-Cyanoisotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoprotodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanometodesnitazene](#), [5-Cyanoetazene](#).

Information on the pharmacology and toxicology of 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene, as well as a whole range of its analogs, is absent. Based on the structural similarity of 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy

Desnitazene to other, more studied opioids, it can be assumed that it will also act as a μ -opioid receptor agonist. Also, based on the published metabolism of Isotonitazene, it can be assumed that 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene is a potential metabolite of [5-Cyanoetazene](#), the appearance of which we reported earlier.

In November 2025, a single offer for the sale of 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene as an analytical standard was identified on the Cayman Chemical trading platform. Monitoring of specialized forums and trading platforms to identify other offers for the substance in question has so far yielded no results. Against the backdrop of heightened interest in new designer opioids and the widespread banning of fentanyls, benzimidazoles in general, and 5-Cyano 4'-hydroxy Desnitazene in particular, have high potential for social danger. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.caymanchem.com/product/43886/5-cyano-4-prime-hydroxy-desnitazene>

Alert publication date: 17.11.2025

IV. Substances used in the synthesis of psychoactive products

80. 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene and 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene

IV. Substances used in the synthesis of psychoactive products

Active ingredient: 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene

Nomenclature name: 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene

Molecular Formula: C₉H₁₀FNO₂

Molecular weight: 183.18

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene.

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene

Nomenclature name: 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene

Molecular Formula: C₉H₁₀FNO₂

Molecular weight: 183.18

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [1-Fluoro-4-\(2-nitropropyl\)benzene](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Recently, in the territory of the Russian Federation, cases of detecting substances 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene and 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene have become more frequent. Both compounds can act as precursors in the synthesis of fluoroamphetamines 4-FA and 3-FA. The synthesis of 4-FA (4-Fluoroamphetamine) from 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene can be carried out using various reducing agents. The presented reduction variant of 1-Fluoro-4-(2-nitropropyl)benzene with formic acid and zinc in isopropyl alcohol is the most optimal and accessible.

Similarly, the synthesis of 3-FA (3-Fluoroamphetamine) from 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene can be carried out. The presented reduction variant of 1-Fluoro-3-(2-nitropropyl)benzene with formic acid and zinc in isopropyl alcohol is the most optimal and accessible.

Monitoring of the spread of the substances continues.

Sources:

1. https://aip sin.com/services/synth_products/6155/
2. <https://www.erowid.org/archive/rhodium/chemistry/pfa.spicybrown.html>

Alert publication date: 27.11.2025

VII. Change in the control status of substances and objects

331. The list of potent substances in the Russian Federation has been updated.

VII. Change in the control status of substances and objects

In accordance with Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated 01.11.2025 No. 1728, the list of potent substances has been expanded. The updated list includes anabolic agents: Androstanol[2,3-c][1,2,5 α]oxadiazol-17 β -ol (chemically similar to furazabol); 5 α -Androstane-3,6,17-trione; 6-Bromoandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione; 11 β -Methyl-19-nortestosterone; 4-Chloro-17 α -methyl-androsta-1,4-diene-3,17 β -diol; 4-Chloro-17 α -methyl-17 β -hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,11-dione. Also added are substances that are selective androgen receptor modulators (SARMs): ligandrol, mastorin, testolone, recardin (SR9011), reverol (SR9009). These substances are actively promoted and used in the sports environment to stimulate muscle growth, improve strength and endurance performance in training, and accelerate fat burning. Uncontrolled use of these drugs can cause significant harm to the life and health of the consumer. Furthermore, 1,4-dimethylpentylamine (1,4-DMAA) has been included in the list under its own heading, previously subject to state control as an isomer of 4-methylhexan-2-amine (DMAA).

Active ingredient: Androstanol[2,3-c][1,2,5 α]oxadiazol-17 β -ol

Nomenclature name: (1S,3aS,3bR,5aS,10aS,10bS,12aS)-10a,12a-Dimethyl-2,3,3a,3b,4,5,5a,6,10,10a,10b,11,12,12a-tetradecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[7,8]phenanthro[2,3-c][1,2,5]oxadiazol-1-ol

Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₂₈N₂O₂

Molecular weight: 316.44

Russian Federation: Androstanol ([2,3-c][1,2,5 α]oxadiazol-17 β -ol) is the name of the position in the List of Potent Substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of Androstanol[2,3-c][1,2,5 α]oxadiazol-17 β -ol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Androstanol\[2,3-c\]\[1,2,5 \$\alpha\$ \]oxadiazol-17 \$\beta\$ -ol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Recardin (SR9011)

Nomenclature name: 3-(((4-Chlorobenzyl)((5-nitrothiophen-2-yl)methyl)amino)methyl)-N-pentylpyrrolidine-1-carboxamide

Molecular Formula: C₂₃H₃₁ClN₄O₃S

Molecular weight: 479.04

Russian Federation: Recardin (SR9011) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of Recardin (SR9011) has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [SR9011](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 4-Chloro-17alpha-methyl-17beta-hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,11-dione

Nomenclature name: (8S,9S,10R,13S,14S,17S)-4-Chloro-17-hydroxy-10,13,17-trimethyl-1,6,7,8,9,10,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-3H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3,11(2H)-dione

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₂₇ClO₃

Molecular weight: 350.88

Russian Federation: 4-Chloro-17alpha-methyl-17beta-hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,11-dione - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: state control over the circulation of 4-Chloro-17alpha-methyl-17beta-hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,11-dione has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [4-Chloro-17alpha-methyl-17beta-hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,11-dione](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 4-Chloro-17alpha-methylandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17beta-diol

Nomenclature name: (8R,9S,10R,13S,14S,17S)-4-Chloro-10,13,17-trimethyl-6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-3H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3,17-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₂₉ClO₂

Molecular weight: 336.9

Russian Federation: 4-Chloro-17alpha-methylandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17beta-diol - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 4-Chloro-17alpha-methylandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17beta-diol has not been established.

Подробнее в AIPSIN: 4-Chloro-17alpha-methylandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17beta-diol

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Reveral (SR9009)

Nomenclature name: Ethyl 3-(((4-chlorobenzyl)((5-nitrothiophen-2-yl)methyl)amino)methyl)pyrrolidine-1-carboxylate

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₂₄ClN₃O₄S

Molecular weight: 437.9

Russian Federation: Reveral (SR9009) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the turnover of Reveral (SR9009) has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [SR9009](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 6-Bromandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione

Nomenclature name: (8R,9S,10R,13S,14S)-6-Bromo-10,13-dimethyl-7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16-decahydro-3H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3,17(6H)-dione

Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₂₃BrO₂

Molecular weight: 363.29

Russian Federation: 6-Bromandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 6-Bromandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione has not been established.

Подробнее в AIP SIN: 6-Bromandrosta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 11beta-Methyl-19-nortestosterone

Nomenclature name: (8R,9S,10R,11S,13S,14S,17S)-17-Hydroxy-11,13-dimethyl-1,2,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-3H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-3-one

Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₂₈O₂

Molecular weight: 288.42

Russian Federation: 11beta-Methyl-19-nortestosterone - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: government control over the circulation of 11beta-Methyl-19-nortestosterone has not been established.

Подробнее в AIP SIN: 11beta-Methyl-19-nortestosterone

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Ligandrol (LGD-4033)

Nomenclature name: 4-{{(2R)-2-[(1R)-2,2,2-Trifluoro-1-hydroxyethyl]pyrrolidin-1-yl}-2-(trifluoromethyl)benzonitrile

Molecular Formula: C₁₄H₁₂F₆N₂O

Molecular weight: 338.2

Russian Federation: Ligandrol (LGD-4033) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: government control over the circulation of LGD-4033 has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [LGD-4033](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Testolone (RAD-140)

Nomenclature name: 2-Chloro-4-(((1R,2S)-1-[5-(4-cyanophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]-2-hydroxypropyl)amino)-3-methylbenzonitrile

Molecular Formula: C₂₀H₁₆ClN₅O₂

Molecular weight: 393.8

Russian Federation: Testolone (RAD-140) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: government control over the circulation of Testolone (RAD-140) has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [RAD140](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1,4-Dimethylpentylamine (1,4-DMAA)

Nomenclature name: 5-Methylhexan-2-amine

Molecular Formula: C₇H₁₇N

Molecular weight: 115.22

Russian Federation: 1,4-Dimethylpentylamine (1,4-DMAA) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 1,4-Dimethylpentylamine has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [1,4-Dimethylpentylamine](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 5alpha-Androstane-3,6,17-trione

Nomenclature name: (5S,8R,9S,10R,13S,14S)-10,13-Dimethyldodecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3,6,17(2H)-trione

Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₂₆O₃

Molecular weight: 302.41

Russian Federation: 5alpha-Androstane-3,6,17-trione - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 5alpha-Androstan-3,6,17-trione has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [5alpha-Androstane-3,6,17-trione](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Masterin (S23)

Nomenclature name: (2S)-3-(4-Chloro-3-fluorophenoxy)-N-[4-cyano-3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]-2-hydroxy-2-methylpropanamide

Molecular Formula: C₁₈H₁₃ClF₄N₂O₃

Molecular weight: 416.75

Russian Federation: Mastorin (S23) - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: state control over the circulation of Mastorin (S23) has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [Mastorin](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Sources:

1. [Постановление Правительства Российской Федерации от 01.11.2025 № 1728 "О внесении изменений в постановление Правительства Российской Федерации от 29 декабря 2007 г. № 964"](#)

Operator: HI **Alert publication date:** 14.11.2025

332. Changes have been made to the lists of narcotic and psychotropic substances in the Republic of Lithuania.

VII. Change in the control status of substances and objects

In accordance with the Order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Lithuania dated 17.06.2025 No. V-571, amendments were made to List I of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances prohibited for medical use, except in cases where substances included in List I are part of a registered medicinal product. New entries included in the list:

Active ingredient: Δ 9-THC-methylcarbonate

Nomenclature name: Methyl ((6aR,10aR)-6,6,9-trimethyl-3-pentyl-6a,7,8,10a-tetrahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromen-1-yl) carbonate

Molecular Formula: C₂₃H₃₂O₄

Molecular weight: 372.5

Russian Federation: Δ 9-THC-methylcarbonate - List I Narcotic drugs, subject to state control as a derivative of Δ 9-THC.

Republic of Belarus: Δ 9-THC-methyl carbonate - List I of dangerous psychotropic substances, subject to state control, like Δ 9-THC ester.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Δ9-THC-methylcarbonate](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabinol (10-OH-HHC)

Nomenclature name: 6,6,9-Trimethyl-3-pentyl-6a,7,8,9,10,10a-hexahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromene-1,10-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₂O₃

Molecular weight: 332.48

Russian Federation: State control over the circulation of 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabinol has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabinol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabinol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Δ9-TTK AC (Delta-9-THC-O-acetate)

Nomenclature name: (6aR,10aR)-6,6,9-Trimethyl-3-pentyl-6a,7,8,10a-tetrahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromen-1-yl acetate

Molecular Formula: C₂₃H₃₂O₃

Molecular weight: 356.5

Russian Federation: Δ 9-THC AC - Schedule I Narcotic drugs, subject to government control as Δ 9-THC ester.

Republic of Belarus: Δ 9-THC AC - List 1 of especially dangerous psychotropic substances, subject to state control as an ester of Δ 9-THC.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Delta-9-THC-O-acetate](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabiphorol (10-OH-HHC-P)

Nomenclature name: 3-Heptyl-6,6,9-trimethyl-6a,7,8,9,10,10a-hexahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromene-1,10-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₃H₃₆O₃

Molecular weight: 360.5

Russian Federation: State control over the circulation of 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabiphorol has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of 10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabiphorol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [10-Hydroxyhexahydrocannabiphorol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1P-AL-LAD

Nomenclature name: (6aR,9R)-7-Allyl-N,N-diethyl-4-propionyl-4,6,6a,7,8,9-hexahydroindolo[4,3-fg]quinoline-9-carboxamide

Molecular Formula: C₂₅H₃₁N₃O₂

Molecular weight: 405.53

Russian Federation: 1P-AL-LAD - List I Narcotic drugs, subject to state control as a derivative of lysergic acid.

Republic of Belarus: state control over the circulation of 1P-AL-LAD has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [1P-AL-LAD](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Homomazindol

Nomenclature name: 6-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2,3,4,6-tetrahydropyrimido[2,1-a]isoindol-6-ol

Molecular Formula: C₁₇H₁₅ClN₂O

Molecular weight: 298.77

Russian Federation: government control over the circulation of Gomomazindol has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: government control over the circulation of Gomomazindol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Gomomazindol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Cychlorphine

Nomenclature name: 3-(3-(1-(1-(4-Chlorophenyl)ethyl)piperidin-4-yl)-2-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)propanenitrile

Molecular Formula: C₂₃H₂₅ClN₄O

Molecular weight: 408.92

Russian Federation: State control over the circulation of Cichlorphine has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of Cichlorphine has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Cychlorphine](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1S-LSD

Nomenclature name: N,N-Diethyl-7-methyl-4-(3-(trimethylsilyl)propanoyl)-4,6,6a,7,8,9-hexahydroindolo[4,3-fg]quinoline-9-carboxamide

Molecular Formula: C₂₆H₃₇N₃O₂Si

Molecular weight: 451.7

Russian Federation: 1S-LSD - List I Narcotic drugs, subject to state control as a derivative of lysergic acid.

Republic of Belarus: state control over the circulation of 1S-LSD has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [1S-LSD](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: Spirochlorphine

Nomenclature name: 8-[1-(4-Chlorophenyl)ethyl]-1-phenyl-1,3,8-triazaspiro[4.5]decan-4-one

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₂₄ClN₃O

Molecular weight: 369.89

Russian Federation: State control over the circulation of Spirochlorphine has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: State control over the circulation of Spirochlorphine has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Spirochlorphine](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Sources:

1. [Lietuvos Respublikos sveikatos apsaugos ministerija Jsakymas «Dėl Lietuvos Respublikos sveikatos apsaugos ministro 2000 m. sausio 6 d. jsakymo Nr. 5 „Dėl Narkotinių ir psichotropinių medžiagų sąrašų patvirtinimo“ p»keitimo" 2025 m. birželio 17 d. Nr. V-571](#)

Operator: HI **Alert publication date:** 21.11.2025

X. Adulterants

268. Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC)

X. Adulterants

Active ingredient: Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC)

Nomenclature name: (6aR,10aR)-6,6,9-Trimethyl-3-pentyl-6a,7,8,9,10,10a-hexahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromen-1-ol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₂O₂

Molecular weight: 316.48

Russian Federation: Hexahydrocannabinol - Schedule I Narcotic drugs.

Republic of Belarus: Hexahydrocannabinol - List 1 of especially dangerous narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances not used for medical purposes.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [Hexahydrocannabinol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

The compound Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC) is a hydrogenated derivative of Δ^9 -THC. It is a natural phytocannabinoid, which is periodically detected in plants of the Cannabis genus only in trace amounts. Therefore, it is usually produced synthetically. Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC) began to be actively promoted on the recreational product market starting from the second half of 2021. In 2023, Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC) was placed under control in Sweden, Belgium, Poland, Estonia, and Lithuania; in 2024 in the Czech Republic; and in 2025 in the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation.

Research from the early 1940s showed that HHC has an effect similar to Δ^9 -THC but weaker. According to user reports, the spectrum of HHC's effects is similar to that of Δ^9 -THC, but in high doses, the substance produces an effect perceived as unpleasant. Overdose may cause nausea, dizziness, and vomiting. Little is known about the risks and side effects of HHC, and there is no data on long-term consequences of consumption.

We have previously repeatedly reported the detection of the substance Hexahydrocannabinol as an adulterating agent in products containing natural phytocannabinoids. In October 2025, such a case was registered again. As part of the "saferparty" project, an edible product (gummy) declared as containing Cannabidiol was submitted for testing. Analysis showed that its composition contained Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC); Cannabidiol was not detected. HHC can naturally be present in Cannabis products only in very small quantities. In large quantities, as in this sample, HHC is added artificially. There is also a possibility that during the production of HHC, by-products are formed that may be potentially extremely harmful to health.

Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://www.saferparty.ch/warnungen/edible-mit-hhc>
2. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1072/>
3. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1197/>
4. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1219/>
5. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1429/>
6. [Critical review report Hexahydrocannabinol, Expert Committee on Drug Dependence Forty-seventh Meeting Geneva, 14–18 October 2024](#)
7. Daniel J. NasrallahNeil K. Garg, Studies Pertaining to the Emerging Cannabinoid Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC), ACS Chem. Biol. 2023, 18, 2023–2029, doi.org/10.1021/acscchembio.3c00254

Alert publication date: 06.11.2025

269. 4-HO-MET (Methocin)

X. Adulterants

Active ingredient: 4-HO-MET (Methocin)

Nomenclature name: 3-{2-[Ethyl(methyl)amino]ethyl}-1H-indol-4-ol

Molecular Formula: C₁₃H₁₈N₂O

Molecular weight: 218.28

Russian Federation: 4-HO-MET (Methocin) - Schedule I, Narcotic Drugs, controlled as a derivative of 4-Hydroxytryptamine.

Republic of Belarus: 4-HO-MET (Methocin) - List 1 of especially dangerous narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [4-HO-MET \(Methocin\)](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In the second half of 2025, the number of cases of detecting the substance 4-HO-MET (Metocin) as an adulterating agent increased on the recreational product market. For example, from June to November 2025, 9 such cases were registered as part of the "[saferparty.ch](#)" project. Samples of blue-colored liquid in glass containers, declared as containing Psilocybin, were submitted for testing. Analysis of the samples showed the presence of 4-HO-MET (Metocin) as the main API in their composition. Psilocybin was not detected in the composition.

The compound 4-HO-MET (Metocin), based on its chemical structure, belongs to tryptamine derivatives and exhibits properties of a potent hallucinogen with psilocybin-like effects. It appeared on the recreational product market in the early 2000s. In addition to psychedelic and hallucinogenic effects, 4-HO-MET promotes sedation, stimulation, spontaneous sensations, and physical euphoria. It is consumed orally and by smoking. Users typically describe the effects of 4-

HO-MET as more pleasant than those of Psilocybin or Psilocin. They are less "intoxicating," and the visual effects are more pronounced. Psychedelic imagery is described as bright and colorful.

Special attention should be paid to the fact that the active dose of Psilocybin is significantly higher (when taken orally, effects occur at doses around 200 mg) than for 4-HO-MET. The use of such products can lead to a significant increase in the risk of overdose and unpredictable side effects that are dangerous to life. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://aipsin.com/newsubstance/1598/>
2. <https://www.saferparty.ch/warnungen/4-ho-met-verkauft-als-psilocybin25899>
3. <https://www.saferparty.ch/warnungen/4-ho-met-verkauft-als-psilocybin-25819>
4. <https://www.saferparty.ch/warnungen/4-ho-met-verkauft-als-psilocybin-280226-lausanne2592>
5. Lea Wagmann, Sascha K Manier, Markus R Meyer, Can the Intake of a Synthetic Tryptamine be Detected Only by Blood Plasma Analysis? A Clinical Toxicology Case Involving 4-HO-MET, Journal of Analytical Toxicology, Volume 46, Issue 5, June 2022, Pages 567–572, doi.org/10.1093/jat/bkab062

Alert publication date: 13.11.2025

270. Pregabalin

X. Adulterants

Active ingredient: Pregabalin

Nomenclature name: (S)-3-(Aminomethyl)-5-methylhexanoic acid

Molecular Formula: C₈H₁₇NO₂

Molecular weight: 159.13

Russian Federation: Pregabalin - List of potent substances.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of Pregabalin has not been established.

Learn more in AIP SIN: [Pregabalin](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In November 2025, as part of the "drugchecking" project, a sample in the form of a capsule, declared as containing MDA (Tenamfetamine), was submitted for testing. The red-white capsule with inscriptions "PGN 75" and "Pfizer" was in a semi-transparent container shaped like a capsule. Analysis of the capsule's contents showed the presence of Pregabalin in its composition; MDA was not detected. This is not the first case of detecting Pregabalin as an adulterating agent. We previously reported the detection of Pregabalin in samples allegedly containing [3-Methylmethcathinone](#) and [Cocaine](#).

Pregabalin (trade names "Lyrica," "Gabana," "Algerica," "Neogab," "Linbag," "Ogrania," "Zonic," "Pregadol," "Galara") is a medicinal anticonvulsant with analgesic and anxiolytic action, a derivative of gamma-aminobutyric acid. Pregabalin, like gabapentin, belongs to the class of gabapentinoid drugs. Over the past few years, there has been a steady increase in the recreational consumption of Pregabalin, including in the territory of the Russian Federation, which we have reported.

Gabapentinoids are used, for example, by heroin consumers to enhance the effects of opioids, as a substitute for them, or to support opioid withdrawal syndrome. Pregabalin and

gabapentin are sometimes used simultaneously in patients undergoing substitution therapy. Also, there is a worldwide increase in the number of fatalities from its use.

For instance, in England, among all drug-related deaths from 2021 to 2024, Pregabalin ranked fourth in prevalence among substances identified at autopsy and second among drugs contributing to death. Most deaths related to Pregabalin occurred when it was taken simultaneously with other medications, such as methadone or morphine. Pregabalin can enhance the effects of other depressants, such as alcohol, benzodiazepines, opioids, GHB/GBL, and muscle relaxants. Opioids and pregabalin in combination slow down breathing. The emergency antidote naloxone, which works against opioids, cannot neutralize the effects of pregabalin. This can lead to respiratory depression, coma, and death. It also enhances the impairment of mental (cognitive) abilities and motor functions caused by other depressants. Monitoring of the substance's spread continues.

Sources:

1. <https://drugchecking.berlin/aktuelle-warnungen>
2. <https://aipsin.com/news Substance/1822/>
3. <https://aipsin.com/news Substance/1476/>
4. <https://aipsin.com/news Substance/1781/>
5. Anne-Laure Pelissier-Alicot, Nicolas Fabresse, Caroline Sastre, Valérie Baillif-Couniou, Deaths related to the combination of pregabalin and other drugs of abuse: About two cases, *Toxicologie Analytique et Clinique* Volume 34, Issue 3, Supplement, September 2022, Pages S153-S154, doi.org/10.1016/j.toxac.2022.06.259
6. <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-northern-ireland-66579996>

Alert publication date: 14.11.2025

XII. Seizures and/or consumption facts of precursors, psychoactive substances and objects on the territory of CIS countries;

133. Synthetic hashish

XII. Seizures and/or consumption facts of precursors, psychoactive substances and objects on the territory of CIS countries;

Active ingredient: Synthetic hashish

Russian Federation: Control over turnover is determined by those present in the ADV

Republic of Belarus: Control over turnover is determined by those present in the ADV

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

In early October, in the Orenburg region, during operational and investigative measures, an object weighing about 0.7 g in a ziplock bag was identified, resembling hashish in consistency with a very spicy smell and cannabis tones. The presented substance was declared as "synthetic hashish."

During the conducted studies of the sample, it was established that a mixture of cannabinoids of various origins, olivetol, and a "terpene profile" had been applied to a plant base (presumably a mixture of spices like khmeli-suneli). The predominant substances were semi-synthetic cannabinoids: Cannabidiol, 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol, 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol, (6aR,10aR)- $\Delta^9(11)$ -THC, and the synthetic cannabinoid EDMB-4en-PINACA. Also found in the sample composition were (9S)-Hexahydrocannabinol, Δ^8 -iso-THC, $\Delta^4(8)$ -iso-THC, 8,9-Dihydrocannabidiol, (-)-trans- Δ^8 -THC, and a number of other substances in low concentrations.

Compounds 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol and 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol, based on their chemical structure, are hydrogenated derivatives of Cannabidiol (CBD) but differ from Cannabidiol both chemically and pharmacologically. The chemical difference is that, unlike Cannabidiol, Tetrahydrocannabidiol has saturated carbon bonds (cyclohexane ring and isopropyl radical), i.e., Tetrahydrocannabidiol contains 4 more hydrogen atoms than Cannabidiol. Also, Tetrahydrocannabidiol has structural similarity to Δ^9 -THC ((-)-trans- Δ^9 -THC) and its isomer (-)-trans- Δ^8 -THC, which are under International control (Schedule I of the 1971 Convention on Psychotropic Substances). Information on the pharmacological and toxicological properties of the substance is limited. Based on its structural similarity to Δ^9 -THC and Δ^8 -THC, it can be assumed that Tetrahydrocannabidiol will act as a cannabinoid receptor agonist. It has been established that Tetrahydrocannabidiol exhibits moderate affinity for the CB1 receptor with $K_i = 145 \pm 5$ nM, unlike

Cannabidiol, which has insignificant affinity for cannabinoid receptors. In April 2023, an official EWS notification (EU Early Warning System, managed by EMCDDA and Europol) was made regarding Tetrahydrocannabidiol (H4-CBD) as a new psychoactive substance. It was based on the identification of the substance in question in base form in a light brown-colored liquid contained in an e-cigarette (vape pen) seized by Swedish customs at the UPS Mölndal International Postal Center. Both diastereomers were detected in the seized sample: 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol and 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabidiol.

The compound (6aR,10aR)- Δ 9(11)-THC (Δ 11-THC), based on its chemical structure, belongs to semi-synthetic phytocannabinoids and is a positional isomer of Δ 9-THC (by double bond position). In nature, (6aR,10aR)- Δ 9(11)-THC occurs in many Cannabis varieties but in trace amounts insufficient for commercial production. The compound was first synthesized in the 1970s. In studies conducted on mice, it was found to exhibit activity amounting to 1/4 of the efficacy of Δ 9-THC. Currently, numerous offers of various types of products (gummies, vape cartridges, tinctures, etc.) containing (6aR,10aR)- Δ 9(11)-THC (Δ 11-THC) either alone or in combination with other cannabinoids are presented on trading internet platforms. The potential advantages of Δ 11-THC are not yet fully studied. Main effects: relaxation, reduced anxiety, euphoria. Some sellers claim that Δ 11-THC produces effects three times stronger than Δ 9-THC, although there is no scientific evidence to confirm this. According to user descriptions, the duration of its effects will depend not only on the dose but also on the method of substance use. When using vape products, a rapid (occurring within minutes), powerful, and short-term effect is obtained. When using edible food products, effects may occur from 30 minutes to 2 hours but can last several hours longer than when smoked.

The compound EDMB-4en-PINACA, based on its chemical structure, is a synthetic cannabinoid of the 3-carbonylindazole subgroup, is an isomer of MDMB(N)-022 (MDMB-4en-PINACA), for which an official notification was made in 2018, and a structural analog of EDMB(N)-018 (EDMB-PINACA), for which a notification was made in June 2021. EDMB-4en-PINACA is included in the list of substances detected in the United States as early as mid-2021. According to a report provided by NFLIS for the period July–September 2021, this substance was repeatedly identified in several states. In 2022, the substance was also recorded in Europe, as reported in a report by the National Research Laboratory of Slovenia. Monitoring of the spread of such products continues.

Active ingredient: Cannabidiol

Nomenclature name: 2-((1R,6R)-6-Isopropenyl-3-methylcyclohex-2-enyl)-5-pentylbenzene-1,3-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₀O₂

Molecular weight: 314.5

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of Cannabidiol has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of Cannabidiol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [Cannabidiol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: (6aR,10aR)-Δ9(11)-THC

Nomenclature name: (6aR,10aR)-6,6-Dimethyl-9-methylene-3-pentyl-6a,7,8,9,10,10a-tetrahydro-6H-benzo[c]chromen-1-ol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₀O₂

Molecular weight: 314.47

Russian Federation: (6aR,10aR)-Δ9(11)-THC – List I Narcotic drugs, Tetrahydrocannabinols (all isomers) and their derivatives.

Republic of Belarus: (6aR,10aR)-Δ9(11)-THC - List 1 of especially dangerous narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances not used for medical purposes.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [\(6aR,10aR\)-Δ9\(11\)-THC](#).

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: EDMB-4en-PINACA

Nomenclature name: Ethyl (S)-3,3-dimethyl-2-(1-(pent-4-en-1-yl)-1H-indazole-3-carboxamido)butanoate

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₂₉N₃O₃

Molecular weight: 371.48

Russian Federation: EDMB-4en-PINACA – Schedule I Narcotic drugs, subject to control as a derivative of 2-(1-Butyl-1H-indazole-3-carboxamido)acetic acid.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of EDMB-4en-PINACA has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [EDMB-4en-PINACA](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol

Nomenclature name: 2-((1R,2S,5S)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)-5-pentylbenzene-1,3-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₄O₂

Molecular weight: 318.5

Russian Federation: control over the circulation of 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol has not been established.

Republic of Belarus: control over the circulation of 1(S)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol has not been established.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [1\(S\)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Active ingredient: 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol

Nomenclature name: 2-((1R,2S,5R)-2-Isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)-5-pentylbenzene-1,3-diol

Molecular Formula: C₂₁H₃₄O₂

Molecular weight: 318.5

Russian Federation: control over the turnover 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol is not installed.

Republic of Belarus: control over the turnover 1(R)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol is not installed.

Learn more in AIPSIN: [1\(R\)-Tetrahydrocannabinidiol](#)

The substance control status shown corresponds to the date the alert was created.

Sources:

1. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1769/>
2. <https://aipsin.com/news substance/1834/>
3. [ANALYTICAL REPORT EDMB-4en-PINACA \(C21H29N3O3\)](#)

Alert publication date: 03.11.2025

aipsin.com

On matters of co-operation:
info@aipsin.com